

**Youth Encounter Program:
Its Effect on Bullying and
Teenage Pregnancy**

An Action Research Submitted to the
Regional Research Committee
Department of Education
Region 7, Central Visayas

MICHAEL G. HORMACHUELOS, Ph.D.
Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts
Secondary School Principal 1

MARIVIC M. HORMACHUELOS, MAEd-TESS
Bien Unido Central Elementary School
Master Teacher II

Division of Bohol Province
September 2021

ABSTRACT

This action research sought to understand whether the Youth Encounter Program effectively minimized bullying and teenage pregnancy cases among its participants. The locale of this research is at Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries & Arts, a public secondary school in Puerto San Pedro, Bien Unido, Bohol. The researchers collected data via document review of bullying and teenage pregnancy incident reports from the school guidance office and an online survey. The researchers analyzed data to see if the intervention effectively minimized bullying and teenage pregnancy cases. In addition, the results identified the program as very effective in minimizing cases of bullying but not as effective in reducing the chances of teenage pregnancy. In terms of perception, the participants find the program very helpful in their character development while also helping them grow more in faith and morals along with their peers. The participants also perceived the program as an excellent opportunity to develop their relational skills as they shared and reflected on their life situations, feelings and emotions, dreams and aspirations, experiences, family and social relationships, and God-given gifts in a youthful and safe environment. While the findings of this study focused only on bullying and teenage pregnancy, they also gave insight into the effectiveness of the Youth Encounter Program in minimizing other behavioral problems among learners in the new normal school context.

Key Words: Youth Encounter Program, Classroom Action Research, Teenage Pregnancy, Bullying

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We want to express our sincere gratitude and appreciation to the individuals who helped us make this research possible.

To the Almighty Loving Triune God, the Author and Giver of life, the Creator and Lord of the universe, who gave us the knowledge, wisdom, and perseverance to take our talents and abilities to hurdle the challenges of this research.

To Mrs. Amelia Cortidor, Division of Bohol Research Chief, for her technical assistance, guidance, and encouragement throughout this research work.

To Sir Jimmy Bucar and Sir Julius Igot and all members of the Research Technical Working Group members of the Division of Bohol who shared their technical assistance and suggestions to improve this study.

To Mr. Victor T. Bautista, our former Schools District Supervisor of Bien Unido District, who gave us his support and encouragement.

To Dr. Rainelda B. Galula, our current Schools District Supervisor of Bien Unido District, who extended her warm support and encouragement.

To Mrs. Praxedes T. Garcia, School Principal of one of the researchers, who supported this study.

Our beloved kids, Maria Theresa, John Luke, Jon Mikhail, John Raphael, John Gabriel, and Maria Elizabeth, for their inspiration, patience, and understanding as we embarked on this research journey.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	-	i
Abstract	-	ii
Acknowledgement	-	iii
Table of Contents	-	iv
Context and Rationale	-	1
Intervention & Strategy	-	3
Action Research Questions	-	4
Action Research Methods		
• Participants & Other Sources of Data Information	-	5
• Data Gathering Methods	-	6
Discussion of Results and Reflection	-	7
Action Plan	-	13
References	-	14
Financial Report/Liquidation	-	16
Appendices		
• Appendix A - Research Instruments	-	18
• Appendix B – Certificate of Anti-Plagiarism	-	28
• Appendix C – Curriculum Vitae	-	30

CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

Bullying is one of the most pressing challenges in our school, while teenage pregnancy is also a priority concern. As recorded by the school in previous years, there have been cases involving bullying (7 cases in SY 2018-2019, 15 cases in 2019-2020) and teenage pregnancies (6 instances in SY.2018-2019, 18 cases for SY 2019-2020). Therefore, this action research is very timely and needed to give the school administration a research-based investigation as to the effectiveness of its adapted program in addressing the issues of Child Protection.

In school-aged adolescents, bullying has become a critical health issue (Graham, 2016). It also affects academic and socio-emotional development (Davis et al., 2019). It is important to note that there is a dynamic interaction between those who are involved in bullying. As the bully increases in strength, the victim loses power. As a result, the victim finds it difficult to respond or cope with the problem (Swearer & Hymel, 2015). It affects negatively not only the victim but also the bully and witnesses as well. While extensive research has been conducted on bullying and victimization in high-income countries, far less research is being done in low- and middle-income countries (Zych, Ortega, & Del Rey, 2015).

Teenage pregnancy is a worldwide phenomenon. Therefore, there are many awareness campaigns to lessen its occurrence. As a result, there is an increasing

worldwide trend for this phenomenon each year. The Philippines is one of the Asian countries which shares a similar situation.

In a study conducted by the National Demographic and Health Survey in 2017, 9% of Filipino women aged 15-19 have begun childbearing: 7% are already mothers, and an additional 2% are pregnant with their first child. The percentage of young women who have begun childbearing is lower in urban areas than in rural areas (7% versus 10%). Young women with primary education and those from the poorest households are more likely to have begun childbearing than those with higher education levels and those from the wealthiest families.

Social development issues such as insufficient education and poverty are often cited as contributors to teenage pregnancy. Moreover, this often results in single parenthood, which renders the mothers to become irresponsible. There is a social stigma associated with this phenomenon in various countries and cultures.

In the Philippines, unintended teenage pregnancy is an ever-present problem. Adolescents are greatly affected by teenage pregnancy may it be in their physical, emotional, social, or spiritual well-being. In addition, it carries additional health risks to both the mother and the baby (Parungao et al., 2014).

It is in this context that Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts (PCPGTVSFA) as a secondary school must install programs by which the guidelines by DEPED on child protection shall have complied. Adopting anti-bullying

policies is a constant call by the Department of Education (DepEd). As per DepEd Order No. 40, series 2012, or the "DepEd Child Protection Policy," there should be zero tolerance against any form of violence against children. Further, the said order established a Child Protection Committee (CPC) in all public and private schools.

Henceforth, Rule IV of DepEd Order No. 55, series 2013 mandates that schools implement bullying prevention programs. Such programs should not only be comprehensive and multifaceted but also involve stakeholders. Lastly, schools should develop intervention strategies like counseling and other character-building activities to enhance learners' psychological, emotional, and psychosocial well-being.

INTERVENTION & STRATEGY

This study utilized the Youth Encounter Program as used in the Diocesan Youth Ministry of the Diocese of Talibon. The school-based *Youth Encounter Program* was a weekend program that provided the student participants to grow in faith and morals with their peers. In addition, it provided a venue where they can share, reflect, and exercise their life situations, feelings and emotions, dreams and aspirations, experiences, family and social relationships, and God-given gifts in a youthful environment. This intervention used modified lectures, self-reflection time, and group sharing on predetermined topics such as self-awareness, spirituality, interpersonal relationships, and conflict management.

The researchers designed the program to enhance the spiritual, psychological, emotional, and psychosocial well-being of the youth, helping them realize the value of

life and how best to use it not just for the self but also for the service of others. The program's goal was for the participants to make a conscious effort to live a morally good life and make a difference in the lives of others. As a result, the program has built a solid moral foundation among its participants, intended to help minimize bullying and teenage pregnancies in the school setting.

ACTION RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researchers designed this study to determine the effectiveness of the *Youth Encounter Program* in minimizing cases of bullying and teenage pregnancies in Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts using descriptive statistics.

Specifically, the answer to the following questions was sought:

1. How many bullying and teenage pregnancy cases were there before and after implementing the Youth Encounter Program?
2. How effective was the Youth Encounter Program in minimizing the number of cases of bullying and teenage pregnancy?
3. Is there a significant difference in bullying and teenage pregnancy instances before and after the Youth Encounter Program?
4. Finally, what action steps can be proposed to strengthen the program further?

ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

The Youth Encounter Program was part of the continuous improvement programs of the school as outlined in the School Improvement Plan. It was a program envisioned to help minimize the cases of bullying and teenage pregnancy in the school. The researchers conducted a document review and an online survey to see if there were a decrease in bullying and teenage pregnancy cases before and after the program's implementation. Based on the findings, the researchers drew a plan of action for continuous improvement of the program.

a. Participants and other Sources of Data

The participants in this action research were Grade 10 and Grade 12 students of Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts for the school year 2019-2020 and 2020-2021. In total, 303 students participated in the program, composed of 158 males and 145 females. The participants were all residents of the Municipality of Bien Unido, Bohol. All participants joined the program voluntarily. The primary data sources for the study were the number of actual documented cases of bullying and teenage pregnancies as reflected in the anecdotal records of the teachers for the school year 2018-2019 (before the program) and 2019-2020 (after the program).

Table 1 shows the total number of participants who took part in the Youth Encounter Program for the school year 2019-2020.

Table 1. The Participants of the Research

Grade Level/Section	Male	Female	Total
G10-Orosa	10	13	23
G10-Del Mundo	8	17	25
G10-Laurel	28	18	46
G10-Arroyo	11	20	31
G10-Quezon	15	3	18
G10-Garcia	20	18	38
G10-Magsaysay	25	20	45
G12-Emerald	12	22	34
G12-Amethyst	29	14	43
Total	158	145	303

An online survey was also conducted to supplement additional data on the interventions' perceived effectiveness among 27 randomly selected participants who rated using a Likert scale. The randomly selected participants also responded to open-ended questions that served as the basis for future studies using qualitative analysis of the intervention's effectiveness.

b. Data Gathering Methods

In this study, the researchers utilized Quasi-Experimental (quantitative approach) in gathering the needed data. First, the researchers did a document review of Anecdotal Records, Bullying/Teenage Pregnancy Incidence Reports, and Guidance Records in the last two school years (SY. 2019-2020, SY. 2020-2021). Then, the researchers tallied the bullying and teenage pregnancy incidents for both school years to gauge the effectiveness of the implemented intervention.

Due to the restrictions of the covid 19 pandemic, the researchers conducted an online survey among the participants to collect additional data on the perceived effectiveness of the intervention instead of focus group discussions and face-to-face interviews.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

In this research, the researchers employed descriptive statistical methods for analyzing the data. First, the data gathered from the school document review was collected and made into a tabular form where the researchers computed the mean difference to test the effectiveness of the intervention.

Table 2. Computed Values for Bullying & Pregnancy Cases Using Mean Difference

Year & Section	BULLYING CASES		PREGNANCY CASES	
	2018-2019	2019-2020	2018-2019	2019-2020
G10-Orosa	4	2	0	0
G10-Del Mundo	0	0	0	0
G10-Laurel	0	0	1	1
G10-Arroyo	3	0	0	1
G10-Quezon	0	1	0	0
G10-Garcia	0	0	0	0
G10-Magsaysay	4	0	0	0
G12-Emerald	0	0	3	1
G12-Amethyst	0	0	1	1
TOTAL	11	3	5	4
Weighted Mean	1.222	0.333	0.556	0.444
Mean Difference	8		0.111	

Table 2 shows the weighted means of bullying and pregnancy cases for the School Year 2019-2020 and School Year 2020-2021. From Table 2, the mean difference value of 8 tells us that the Youth Encounter Program effectively minimized the cases of bullying but was not as effective in reducing cases of pregnancy as it has only a mean difference of 0.111.

Table 3. Computed Values - Bullying Cases (Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test)

2018-2019 (Before)	2019-2020 (After)	Difference	/D/	Rank	Signed Rank
4	2	2	2	7	p7
0	0	0	0	3	3
0	0	0	0	3	3
3	0	3	3	8	p8
0	1	-1	1	6	n6
0	0	0	0	3	3
4	0	4	4	9	p9
0	0	0	0	3	3
0	0	0	0	3	3

Table 3 shows in tabular form the data gathered from the document review on the number of bullying cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program. It also shows the difference, rank, and signed-rank values.

To test if there is a significant difference in the number of bullying cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test was used since the population was not normally distributed. Based on the statistical computations, the critical value = 6 and the computed value = 6, with $n = 9$, at $\alpha = 0.5$. Since the critical

value and the computed value are equal, the results show a significant difference in the number of bullying cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program.

Table 4. Computed Values - Pregnancy Cases (Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test)

2018-2019 (Before)	2019-2020 (After)	Difference	/D/	Rank	Signed Rank
0	0	0	0	4	4
0	0	0	0	4	4
1	1	0	0	4	4
0	1	-1	1	8	n8
0	0	0	0	4	4
0	0	0	0	4	3
0	0	0	0	4	4
3	1	2	2	9	p9
0	0	0	0	4	4

Table 4 shows in tabular form the data gathered from the document review on the number of pregnancy cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program. It also shows the difference, rank, and signed-rank values.

To test if there is a significant difference in the number of pregnancy cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test was used since the population was not normally distributed. Based on the statistical computations, the critical value = 6 and the computed value = 8, with $n = 9$, at $\alpha = 0.5$. Since the critical value is less than the computed value, the results show no significant difference in pregnancy cases before and after the Youth Encounter Program.

Chart 1. Becoming A Better Person.

The following charts come from the online survey that was conducted with 27 participants who randomly responded. Chart 1 shows the participants' responses to question 1 with a focus on becoming a better person. Based on Chart 1, 92.6% totally agree, while 7.4% slightly agree that participating in the Youth Encounter Program helped them become a better person afterward.

Chart 2. Avoiding Bullying Tendencies

Chart 2 shows the responses of the participants to question number 2, focusing on avoiding bullying tendencies. Based on the chart, 81.5% totally agree, while 18.5%

slightly agree that the Youth Encounter Program helped them avoid bullying tendencies after attending it.

Chart 3. Avoiding Immoral Tendencies Leading to Teenage Pregnancy

Chart 3 shows the participants' responses to question number 3, focusing on avoiding teenage pregnancy tendencies. Again, the chart shows that 88.9% totally agree, 7.4% slightly agree, and 3.7% totally disagree that the Youth Encounter Program helped them avoid immoral tendencies that lead to teenage pregnancy.

Chart 4. Recommending the Youth Encounter Program

Chart 4 shows the participants' responses to question number 4, focusing on whether they will recommend the Youth Encounter Program to their friends and schoolmates after having experienced it themselves. The chart shows that 92.6% totally agree that they will recommend the Youth Encounter Program to their friends and schoolmates, with only 7.4% saying they slightly agree.

The researchers found a 72% decrease (from 11 in SY 2019-2020 to 3 in Sy 2020-2021) in the number of bullying incidents. Additionally, results show a 20% decrease in the number of pregnancy cases (from 5 in SY 2019-2020 to 4 in 2020-2021) after implementing the Youth Encounter Program. Thus, the results show that the program is an excellent intervention in minimizing cases of bullying but not as effective in reducing cases of teenage pregnancy. Moreover, as the data analysis shows, it is an effective program for character, spiritual, emotional, and relational development.

Based on the results of the research, the researchers reached the following reflections:

1. The researchers should continue to study the Youth Encounter Program in the new normal as it certainly helps in overall character development among learners.
2. Class advisers and school administration should give the Youth Encounter Program to other year levels to extend its reach to more learners.
3. Thorough monitoring and evaluation will help improve the Youth Encounter Program to sustain its gains.

4. Due to time constraints, the researchers need further research to analyze all the other data gathered but not included in this study.
5. Minimizing bullying and teenage pregnancy using character development programs such as the Youth Encounter is doable, but its long-term effectiveness and sustainability need further investigation.

ACTION PLAN

The researchers will disseminate the findings of this study to the teachers, parents, students, and stakeholders through PTA Meetings, Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions, Focused Group Discussions (FGDs), State of the School Address (SOSA), Research Conferences and through In-Service Training of Teachers (INSET).

Moreover, the researchers will share the results of this study as a basis of evaluation on how to further improve the Youth Encounter Program and other related character-building activities for better results.

Finally, the researchers will share this study with aspiring researchers to conduct related studies on character development concerning bullying and teenage pregnancy cases in schools.

REFERENCES

Books

Swearer, S. M., & Hymel, S. (2015). Understanding the psychology of bullying: Moving toward a social-ecological diathesis-stress model. *American Psychologist*, 70, 344–353.10.1037/a0038929

Werth JM, Nickerson AB, Aloe AM, Swearer SM J. (2015 Aug). Bullying victimization and the social and emotional maladjustment of bystanders: A propensity score analysis. *Sch Psychol* 53(4):295-308.

Zych, I., Ortega, R., & Del Rey, R. (2015, September–October). Scientific research on bullying and cyberbullying: Where have we been and where are we going? *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 24, 188–198.10.1016/j.avb.2015.05.015

Internet

DepEd Order No. 40, series 2012 or the "DepEd Child Protection Policy"

<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/05/14/do-40-s-2012-deped-child-protection-policy/>

DepEd Order No. 55, series 2013 or the "Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 10627 (RA 10627) Otherwise Known as the "Anti-Bullying Act of

2013," <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2018/12/21/statement-on-prevention-of-bullying-in-public-and-private-schools/>

Graham S. (2016). Victims of bullying in schools. *Theory and Practice*. 55 136–144.
10.1080/00405841.2016.1148988 <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1096850>

Parungao, C. R., Bautista, L. P., Mariano, R., Bonifacio, V. M. & Aguinaldo, M. V.
(2014). Life Brought at a Tender Age: The Lived Experiences of Filipino Teenage
<https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=5747>

2017 Philippine National Demographic and Health Survey Key Findings: Retrieved
from <http://tiny.cc/6bu3kz>

Molina, P., *The Youth Encounter (Virac Model)*, 1986
<http://youthencounterblog.blogspot.com/>

Homegrown Filipino youth ministry model (the Virac model)
https://www.bosco.link/mailnews_old/34124

Financial Report and Liquidation

LIQUIDATION REPORT Basic Education Research Fund (BERF) First Tranche (PhP 10,346.40)

SUMMARY OF EXPENSES

Title of Research: Youth Encounter Program: Effect on Bullying & Teenage Pregnancy

Date	Particulars	Reference (OR# / SV#)	Amount (PhP)
3/13/2020	Traveling Expenses for the Submission of the Approved Title and Write-up		600.00
3/14/2020	Expenses for Mobile Load	12169	500.00
3/15/2020	Expenses for Mobile Load	12172	500.00
7/16/2020	Traveling Expenses for the Submission of Signed MOA for BERF Funding		600.00
9/15/2020	Expenses for the Office Supplies	1368	3,962.00
9/16/2020	Expenses for the Office Supplies	869	1,428.00
9/16/2020	Expenses for Mobile Load	870	1,000.00
1/18/2021	Traveling Expenses of the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires		600.00
2/22/2021	Traveling Expenses of the Retrieval of Survey Questionnaires		600.00
3/9/2021	Traveling Expenses for the Conduct of Interviews		600.00
SUB-TOTAL			10,390.00
GRAND TOTAL			10,390.00

Prepared by:

MICHAEL G. HORMACHUELOS, Ph.D.

Lead Proponent
Name & Signature

MARIVIC M. HORMACHUELOS

2nd Proponent
Name & Signature

Date:

Certified Correct:

RAINELDA GALULA, Ph.D.

Lead Proponent's Immediate Supervisor

Representative from Finance Unit
School Division Research Committee Member

Appendix A. Research Instrument

Youth Encounter Program Effectiveness - Online Survey

Prepared By: Michael G. Hormachuelos, Ph.D., Marivic M. Hormachuelos, MAED-TESS

This online survey form will capture data on the Youth Encounter Program implementation effectiveness for the participants involved in the program at Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. School of Fisheries and Arts for SY 2019-2020.

Dear respondent,

This questionnaire intends to help determine your perception of the effectiveness of the Youth Encounter Program implemented at Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. School of Fisheries and Arts for SY 2019-2020. Thus, it may serve as an objective basis for future related guidance programs. Given this, please give an honest assessment of the program. Kindly check the column that best reflects your answer/perception. Thank you for your generous cooperation.

* Required

Email *: _____

I. UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF LIFE & WELL-BEING

Direction: Read each statement carefully and assess your level of proficiency based on the scale below:

Response Interpretation	
Highly Understood Program is highly effective	Youth Encounter
Adequately Understood Program is adequately effective	Youth Encounter
Slightly Understood Program is slightly effective	Youth Encounter
Not Understood Program is slightly effective	Youth Encounter

1A. Understood the importance of spiritual well-being. (BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

1B. Understood the importance of spiritual well-being. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

2A. 1A. Understood the importance of emotional well-being. (BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

2B. Understood the importance of emotional well-being. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

3A. Understood the importance of physical well-being. (BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

3B. Understood the importance of physical well-being. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

4A. Understood the importance of good relationships. (BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

4B. Understood the importance of good relationships. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

5A. Understood the importance and value of life. (BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

5B. Understood the importance and value of life. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

6A. Understood the importance and value of living a moral life. (BEFORE the YE Program)

*

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

6B. Understood the importance and value of living a moral life. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

7A. Understood the importance and value of living a life in love and service to others.
(BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

7B. Understood the importance and value of living a life in love and service to others.
(AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

8A. Understood the importance of building a solid moral foundation as a young person.
(BEFORE the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
 Slightly
 Understood
 Understood
Highly Understood

8B. Understood the importance and value of building a solid moral foundation as a young person. (AFTER the YE Program) *

Mark only one oval.

- Not Understood
- Slightly
- Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

B. OVERALL EVALUATION OF THE YOUTH ENCOUNTER PROGRAM

Kindly give your overall evaluation of the Youth Encounter Program by selecting the appropriate statement of choice.

1. Participating in the Youth Encounter Program helped me become a better person than before participating in it. *

Mark only one oval.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree
- Totally Disagree
- Other:

2. Participating in the Youth Encounter Program helped me avoid bullying tendencies more than before participating in it. *

Mark only one oval.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree
- Totally Disagree
- Other:

3. Participating in the Youth Encounter Program helped me to avoid immoral tendencies that will lead to teenage pregnancy more than before participating in it. *

Mark only one oval.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree
- Totally Disagree
- Other:

4. Participating in the Youth Encounter Program is something that I will recommend to my friends and schoolmates. *

Mark only one oval.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree
- Totally Disagree
- Other:

Direction: This part intends to explore and describe your significant experiences, thoughts, and feelings during the three-day Youth Encounter Program. Your comments and narratives may serve as an objective basis for future related guidance training and seminars.

I.FOCUS
QUESTIONS

In view of this, please assess yourself with utmost honesty and credibility. Kindly answer the following questions according to how you truly feel and best reflects your perception. Thank you for your generous cooperation.

1. How do you describe your experiences and thoughts about the effectiveness and usefulness of the Youth Encounter Program? *

2. Can you describe your learning before, during, and after the Youth Encounter Program? *

3. What significant changes or transformations happened to your spiritual, emotional, mental, and social skills after the Youth Encounter Program? *

4. What difficulties and challenges did you encounter in your participation in the Youth Encounter Program? *

5. What can you suggest in improving the implementation of the Youth Encounter Program? *

THANK YOU SO MUCH FOR YOUR RESPONSES!

Appendix B. Certificate of Anti-Plagiarism

We, Michael G. Hormachuelos and Marivic M. Hormachuelos, understand that plagiarism is the act of taking and using another's ideas and works and passing them off as one's own. This includes explicitly copying the whole work of another person and/or using some parts of their work without proper acknowledgment and referencing.

We hereby attest to the originality of this completed research with a similarity index of 12% using the Turnitin Plagiarism Detection Tool and have cited properly all the references used. We further commit that all deliverables and the final research study emanating from this study are original content. Therefore, we use appropriate citations in referencing others' works from various sources.

We understand that validation from this declaration and commitment shall be subject to consequences and dealt with accordingly by the Department of Education. Anyone found to have committed plagiarism will be blocked listed from availing of any other research grant mechanism in the Department.

MICHAEL G. HORMACHUELOS
Lead Researcher
Date: September 22, 2021

MARIVIC M. HORMACHUELOS
Co-Researcher
Date: September 22, 2021

Similarity Index: 12%
Detection Tool Used: Turnitin
Date of Plagiarism Check: September 22, 2021

AR - Youth Encounter Program_Michael & Marivic Hormachuelos

ORIGINALITY REPORT

12%	11%	2%	8%
SIMILARITY INDEX	INTERNET SOURCES	PUBLICATIONS	STUDENT PAPERS

PRIMARY SOURCES

1	legacy.senate.gov.ph Internet Source	2%
2	www.coursehero.com Internet Source	2%
3	www.teacherph.com Internet Source	2%
4	www.deped.gov.ph Internet Source	1%
5	www.tandfonline.com Internet Source	1%
6	Submitted to Montclair State University Student Paper	1%
7	newsprod.abs-cbnnews.com Internet Source	1%
8	Submitted to Mindanao State University - IIT Student Paper	<1%
9	clubmanila.files.wordpress.com Internet Source	<1%